

CT Angiographic Study for Evaluation of Pulmonary Embolism in Pondicherry Population

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Abstract:

Background: Pulmonary embolism is an important cause of morbidity and mortality, despite advancements in clinical understanding and diagnostic facilities. Hence, CT angiography evaluation is an ideal tool for diagnosis pulmonary embolism (PE).

Method: 45 adult patients aged between 20-70 years with PE were studied. The angiography was done with a 256-slice CT scanner. The intravenous Contrast administered was non-ionic, low-osmolar iodinated contrast medium, Iopamira 300 mg iodine/ml.

Results: A high prevalence of PE was observed in 41–50 age groups. The highest clinical manifestation was respiratory distress 42 (93.3%) followed by chest pain, 37% and least was hemoptysis. The highest location of emboli was 20 (44.4%) central, followed by 12 (26.6%) lobar, and the least was 4 (8.8%) sub-segmental. The highest associated risk factor was 37 (82.2%) immobility, followed by 34 (75.5%) H/O surgery, and the least was 12 (26.6%) COPD.

Conclusion: A CTA study is an ideal tool to evaluate pulmonary embolism, but clinicians should be aware of the accuracy and limitations of the test. Diagnostic algorithms will be helpful for diagnostic strategy.

Keywords: Pulmonary Embolism, Deep Venous Thrombosis, 256-Segment CT Scanner, Iodinated Contrast Medium, Respiratory Distress.

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Introduction

Pulmonary embolism (PE) is the third most common acute cardio-vascular disease after myocardial infarction, and stroke results in thousands of deaths each year because it often goes undetected [1]. The diagnostic tests for thromboembolic disease include (a) the D-dimer assay, which has high sensitivity but poor specificity; (b) ventilation perfusion scintigraphy, which also has high scintigraphy sensitivity but poor specificity. (c) Computed tomographic (CT) pulmonary angiography has been elevated with meta-analysis.

Pulmonary angiography is the diagnostic standard for confirming embolism (CT pulmonary), diagnostic criteria for acute and chronic pulmonary embolism, and causes of misdiagnosis of pulmonary embolism [2].

The misdiagnosis group includes patient-related factors, i.e., respiratory motion artifacts, image noise from a pulmonary artery catheter, and flow-related artifacts. The technical factors include window settings, streak artifacts, lung algorithm artifacts, partial volume artifacts, and stair step artifacts [3]. The anatomic factors are vascular bifurcation and misidentification of veins.

The pathological factors are mucous plug, perivascular edema, and pulmonary artery sarcoma [4]. It needs a trained radiologist to diagnose pulmonary embolism based on its location. Hence, an attempt was made to evaluate the pulmonary embolism in different age groups, its clinical features, and the location of the embolism.

Material and Method

45 (forty-five) patients aged between 20 to 70 years visited the Sri Venkateshwara Medical College Hospital Pondicherry-605102 were studied.

Inclusion Criteria: Suspected pulmonary embolism patients were referred to radiology for diagnosis. The patients who gave their consent in writing for the study were selected for the study.

Exclusion Criteria: Patients already on treatment for P.E. and patients below 20 years of age were excluded from the study.

Method: All the patients underwent routine blood examination and CT angiography of the lungs for the detection of pulmonary embolism. All the computer topographic angiogram scans (CTPA) were done with a 256-slice CT scanner (SOMATOM Definition Flash, Siemens Healthineers, Erlangen, Germany) following standard protocol. The scans were performed in the pulmonary arterial phase with a 0.5-mm slice thickness reconstructed at 1.0 mm thickness, a KV of 100 to 200, and autoMA.

The intravenous contrast administered was non-ionic, low-osmolar iodinated contrast medium, Iopamiro (Bracco, Milan, Italy), 300 mg iodine/ml.

The volume of contrast used was 50 to 70 ml at a rate of 5 ml/second, followed by 20 ml of normal saline at the same rate after multi-planar reconstruction was done. The details of age, sex, and risk factors were noted.

The duration of the study was from August 2023 to June 2024.

Statistical Analysis: Classification of patients as per age, clinical manifestation locations, and associated risk factors were made with percentage. The statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software. The ratio of males and females was 2:1.

Observation and Results

Table 1: Distribution of patients as per age 4 (8.8%) 20-30, 7 (15.5%), 31-40, 19 (42.2%) 41-50, 9 (20%) 51-60, 6 (13.3%) >60 years of age.

Table 2: Clinical manifestations of the pulmonary embolism patients 42 (93.3%) had respiratory distress, 37 (82.2%) had chest pain, 30 (66.6%) had hemoptysis, and 27 (60%) had tachycardia.

Table 3: CT angiographic distribution of patients as the location of embolism: 20 (44.4%) central, 12 (26.6%) lobar, 9 (20%) segmental, and 4 (8.8%) sub-segment.

Table 4: Associated risk factors in pulmonary embolism patients 37 (82.2%) Immobility, 34 (7%) had a history of surgery, and 31 (68.8%) had a history of trauma. 24 (53.3%) had DVT, and 22 (48.8%) had obesity (BMI >30). 18 (40%) had a history of contraceptive use, 12 (26.6%) had contraceptive use, and 12 (26.6%) had COPD.

Table 1: Distribution of the patient as per age

Age	No. of patients (45)	Percentage (%)
20-30	4	8.8
31-40	7	15.5
41-50	19	42.2
51-60	9	20
>60	6	13.3
Total	45	

Figure 1: Distribution of the patient as per age

Table 2: Clinical manifestation of the pulmonary Embolism patients

Clinical manifestation	No. of patients (45)	Percentage (%)
Respiratory distress	42	93.3
Chest pain	37	82.2
Hemoptysis	30	66.6
Tachycardia	27	60

Figure 2: Clinical manifestation of the pulmonary Embolism patients

Table 3: CT Angiographic distribution of patients as per the location of Emboli

Location	No. of patients (45)	Percentage (%)
Central	20	44.4
Lobar	12	26.6
Segmental	9	26
Sub-segmental	4	8.8
Total	45	100

Figure 3: CT Angiographic distribution of patients as per the location of Emboli

Table 4: Study of associated risk factors in pulmonary Embolism patients

Sl. No	Risk factors	No. of patients (45)	Percentage (%)
1	Immobility	37	82.2
2	H/o surgery	34	75.5
3	H/o Trauma	31	68.8
4	Deep venous Thrombosis	24	53.3
5	Obesity (BMI >30)	22	48.8
6	H/o Contraceptive	18	40
7	COPD	12	26.6

Figure 4: Study of associated risk factors in pulmonary Embolism patients

Discussion

Present study of CT angiography for evaluation of PE in Pondicherry population. Pulmonary embolism is observed mainly in 41-50 years old patients: 19 (42.2%), followed by 9 (20%) in 51-60-year-olds, and the least in 4 (8.8%) in 20-30 year-olds (Table 1). The clinical manifestation was 42 (93.3%) respiratory distress, 37 (82.2%) patients had tachycardia and 27 (60%) (Table 2). In the CT angiographic study, the major location of PE was 20 (44.4%) central, followed by 12 (26.6%) lobar, and the least PE was located at 4 (8.8%) in the sub-segmental lobe of the lungs (Table 3). The associated risk factors were 37 (82.2%) were immobility, 34 (75.5%) had a history of surgery, and 31 (68.8%) had H/O of trauma (Table 4). These findings are more or less in agreement with previous studies [5,6,7]. Acute PE diagnostic criteria are that, due to a large filling defect, the artery may be enlarged with adjacent patient vessels. A partial filling defect is surrounded by contrast material, producing the polo mint sign on images acquired perpendicular to the long axis of a vessel and the "railway track" sign on longitudinal images of the vessel. A peripheral luminal filling defect that acutely angles with the arterial wall. In chronic PE, the diagnostic criteria include: (a) complete occlusion of a vessel that is smaller than the adjacent patient vessel. (b) a peripheral, crescent shaped intraluminal defect that forms obtuse angles with the vessel

wall. (c) thickened contrast material in smaller arteries due to reorganisation. (d) Secondary signs include extensive bronchial and other systemic collateral vessels. [8]

It is observed that right ventricular (RV) failure and RV ischemia are the primary etiologies by which early death from acute pulmonary embolism (PE) occurs. Hence, echocardiography is a sensitive tool for diagnosing acute RVD in acute PE (9). Hemodynamic instability, defined as hypotension in presentation, has been used as clinical discrimination between massive and non-massive. Acute PE and as a guide to recommend the use of thrombolytic therapy. Pulmonary angiogram is generally considered to be the most definitive test for the diagnosis of PE [10]. The presence of an intravascular filling defect is considered positive for diagnosing PE. A CT scan is a rapid, non-invasive, safe, and widely used scan that provides significant additional information in patients with cardiopulmonary symptoms [11]. After the invention of helical CT, the first study evaluating its use in PE came from Remmy Jardin et al. in 1992. This study is for the evaluation of the main lobar and segmented vessels when compared with the pulmonary artery (PA). The introduction of CT venography has made CT a single convenient test to diagnose DVT (deep venous thrombosis) and PE [12].

Summary and conclusion

Present CT angiographic study of pulmonary embolism is a gold standard tool to evaluate PE, but clinicians should be aware of the accuracy and limitations of the test. Diagnostic algorithms will be helpful for diagnostic strategy.

Limitation of study: Owing to the to the tertiary location, small number of patients, and lack of the latest techniques, we have limited findings and results.

This research work has been approved by the ethical committee of Srivenkateshwara Medical College and the research center Pondicherry 605102.

References

1. Anderson FA Jr., Wheeler B., and Goldberg RJ: A population-based perspective of the hospital incidence and case fatality rates of deep venous thrombosis and pulmonary embolism, *Arch Intern Med.* 1991, 151; 933–938.
2. Giuntinic C, Ricco GD: Pulmonary Embolism: Epidemiology *Chest* 1995, 107; 3–9.
3. Borris LC, Christiansen HM, Lassen MR: Comparison of real time B mode ultrasonography and bilateral ascending phlebography for detection of postoperative deep vein thrombosis following elective hip surgery. *ThrombHaemost.* 1989, 61; 363–365.
4. Wittram C, Meehan MJ: Trends in thoracic radiology over a decade at a large academic medical center *J. Thoracic Imaging* 2004, 19; 164–170.
5. Remy, Jardin M, Remy J: Diagnosis of central pulmonary embolism with helical CT: role of two-dimensional multiplanar reformation *AJR Am. J. Roentegenol.* 1995, 165; 1131–1138.
6. Wu As, Pezzullo JA: CT pulmonary angiography quantification of pulmonary embolus as a predictor of a patient's initial experience *Radiology* 2004, 203; 831–835.
7. Van Rossum AB, Pattynama PMT: Pulmonary Embolism: Vahadation of stral CT angiography in 149 patients, *Radiology* 1996, 201; 467–470.
8. Davidson SL, Lensing AW: Should echocardiography of the right ventricle help to determine who receives thrombolysis for pulmonary embolism? *Chest* 2001, 120, 6–8.
9. Stein PD, AthanoSouli S, Alavi A: Complications and validity of pulmonary angiography embolism circulation 1992, 85; 462–8.
10. Stein PD, Hull RD: Strategy that includes serial noninvasive leg tests for diagnosis of thrombo-embotic disease in patients with suspected acute pulmonary embolism based on data from PIOPED. *Arch interm Med.* 1995, 155; 2101–4.
11. Wells SP, Roger M: Diagnosis of pulmonary embolism: when imaging is needed, *Clinic Chest Med.* 2003, 24; 13–28.
12. Tamiz LJ: Usefulness of clinical prediction rules for the diagnosis of venous thromboembolism. A systemic review *Am. J. Med.* 2004, 117; 676–84.